

Modeling highly charged universe stability based on half-life of non-primordial unstable isotopes

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Abstract. There is a common consensus that universe has net zero charge, or close to it down to the order 10^{-43} of excess charge density per photon. Also it is currently known that in an early universe evolution there was a Planck epoch when leptons, quarks and gluons were borned exactly so that now for each electron we have $2.6u$ quarks and $2.3d$ quarks, given that most ordinary matter is composed from ${}^1_1\text{H}$, ${}^4_2\text{He}$ atoms. If we form net charge equation for corresponding quarks per electron and electron itself we will see that $2.6q_u + 2.3q_d + e \approx 0$. So it seems that universe at early stages has formed like so that quarks exactly balances electron charge. However it's not clear of why total universe charge must be zero or close to it. In this paper I try to get into this question a bit deeper and at least partially answer it, using analogies from non-primordial isotopes stability.

Using information from wikipedia about isotopes, I have compiled such table of non-primordial isotopes half-life :

Elements with no primordial isotopes		
Z	A	Half-life (s)
43	108	1.30E+14
61	153	5.58E+08
84	210	3.94E+09
85	213	2.91E+04
86	215	3.30E+05
87	218	1.32E+03
88	220	5.04E+10
89	223	6.87E+08
91	228	1.03E+12
93	233	6.75E+13
Z	A	Half-life (s)
94	235	2.54E+15
95	238	2.32E+11
96	240	4.92E+14
97	243	4.35E+10
98	245	2.84E+10
99	248	4.08E+07
100	250	8.68E+06
101	253	4.43E+06
102	255	3.48E+03
103	258	3.96E+04
104	260	4.68E+03
105	263	1.03E+05
106	265	8.40E+02
107	268	6.00E+01
108	270	1.60E+01
109	273	4.50E+00
110	275	1.27E+01
111	278	1.02E+02
112	280	2.80E+01
113	283	9.50E+00
114	285	1.90E+00
115	288	6.50E-01
116	290	5.70E-02
117	293	5.10E-02
118	295	6.90E-04

Table is grouped into two parts, because they have their own separate dynamics, first part may also be interesting, because it follows quadratic law more or less, but for my this reasearch second part is more important, because first part just shows temporary half-life fluctuations between isotopes - half-life never reaches values bigger than that it was started from $Z = 43$ element, within error of one order of magnitude. Mass number A was calculated with formula $A = Z + 1.5Z$. Formula was chosen such because these non-primordial elements are out of stability band, so for them applies neutron ratio rule $\frac{N_n}{N_p} = 1.5$. If we would draw a half-life chart of second table part elements, we would see this :

By analyzing this dynamics, I have come to exponential half-life law :

$$t_{1/2} = \tau e^{-\beta n} \quad (1)$$

where τ is maximum value for half-life, and n is nucleon amount in unstable atom. From data fitting was extrapolated that $\tau = 1.74 \times 10^{72}$ seconds and $\beta = 0.59$. Fitted model is quite good, because has $R^2 = 0.88$. Now we can imagine hypothetical nucleus with the size of whole universe. Using mass of ordinary matter in the universe, which is 1.50×10^{53} kg and average nucleon mass, one can calculate that such universe-sized nucleus would have in total about $n = 10^{79}$ nucleons. Needless to say that putting this number into equation (1) would mess high-precision calculator or computer algebra system with “float underflow” error or similar. However we can use limits trick

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tau}{e^{\beta n}} = 0 \quad (2)$$

to see that such expression amazingly quickly approaches zero. Which means that universe-sized nucleus has 0 sec half-life, or in other words that such big nucleus can't exist at all. Why is that ? It's relatively easy to understand. Protons in a nucleus repels each other apart due to electrostatic force and only the strong

atomic force coming from neutrons - keeps atom as integral unit and don't lets it to break apart. So electrostatic repulsion force and strong nuclear force are competing with each other. From quantum mechanics we know that there's always energy fluctuations, this must include binding energy between nucleons also. So as nucleus gets bigger and bigger, more bigger opposing forces compete and even a slightest fluctuation or other perturbation (such as fluctuation in net electric field given by electrons in atom, etc), can break this sensitive force equilibrium and consequently - break the atom apart. All in all - it must be clear that two opposing things with enormous magnitudes can't exist friendly together in nature by each other.

Conclusions. Using non-primordial isotope half-life information exponential half-life law of such elements was derived (1). It was shown that universe-sized nucleus can't exist (2), because of too great forces compete with each other and as a consequence, drawn from this fact,- highly charged universe can't exist too. That must be the reason why universe laws tends to minimize net charge in it. It also may suggest that such charge equilibrium could instantly be spawned in Planck era between Leptons and Quarks, because it's natural to expect stable "course of things".